

Chemical analysis using a hand-held XRF spectrometer on different types of meteorites including carbonaceous, pallasite, metallic and Martian samples

Livio Rosai, retired physicist (*)¹
Via Varzi 1/24, 20044 Arese (MI), Italy
October 2023

1. Scope of this paper

Scope of the paper is that of analyzing with a hand-held XRF spectrometer the composition of representative samples of different types of meteorites described in point 2, including the rare iron meteorites, the very rare Pallasite and a Martian one. In comparison with the standard ICP-MS techniques for bulk chemical analysis of meteorites, the XRF technique, although less used, has the advantages of simplicity, being non-destructive because not requiring sample preparation and providing quick responses. The results will be compared with literature data (when available) on similar types of meteorites.

2. Brief resumé of principal meteorite types and classifications (for the benefit of not experts in the field) [1]

A meteorite is an object originating from outer space that reaches Earth's ground. Some of the material produced in the early times of the universe and inside the stars mainly during supernova explosions is ejected out into the space, where, due to the gravity attraction, it accumulates as clouds of gas (mostly hydrogen) and dust.

About 4.6 billion years ago, one such cloud (solar nebula) collapsed on itself moving towards its center of mass. This process caused a huge increase of density and, by consequence, of pressure and temperature.

Inside its core hydrogen atoms collided together at temperatures of million degrees, forming helium by nuclear fusion and releasing huge amounts of energy. A new star, our sun, started to shine. Its temperature varies from around 15 million degrees C at the core to 'only' about 5500 degrees C at the surface, the so-called photosphere. The remnants of the abovementioned cloud collapsing process formed a disc of rotating fragments around the newborn star. Eventually the planets and other solar system objects coalesced from these fragments, including asteroids.

Meteorites were formed by collisions between asteroids, or between asteroids and other astronomical objects (Mars, Moon) disintegrating in big and small pieces.

During falling through the Earth's atmosphere the air resistance causes the meteorite to heat up and emit light.

All new meteorites are approved (as genuine), named, classified and recorded in the *Meteoritical Bulletin* by the **The Meteoritical Society**, [2] an international organization dedicated to the promotion of research and education in planetary science with emphasis on the studies of meteorites and other extraterrestrial materials. The Society was established in 1933.

The meteorites can be classified basically into three broad categories depending from their composition [3]:

- a. **Stony meteorites** (97,5%)
- b. **Stony-iron meteorites** (0,6%)
- c. **Iron meteorites** (1,9%)

Stony meteorites, the most abundant type, are classified in

¹ E-mail: livio.rosai@alice.it

Chondrites (93,9%), Achondrites (6,9%). The Chondrites are, in turn, subdivided in Ordinary (93,9%), Carbonaceous (4,6%) and others (1,5%).

The Stony-iron meteorites are made of by Pallasites (0,2%) and Mesosiderites (0,4%).

Chondrites

Chondrites are stony meteorites that have not been modified due to melting or differentiation of the parent body. Chondrites can also be divided depending on iron and nickel concentrations and iron oxide in silicates:

- The H Chondrites have the Highest total iron and nickel (15~20%), but lower iron oxide in the silicates
- The L Chondrites have Lower total iron and nickel (5-11%), but higher iron oxide in the silicates
- The LL Chondrites have Low total iron and nickel (2-5%), but the highest iron oxide content in the silicates

Chondrites can also be categorized according to their petrologic type, which is the degree to which they were thermally metamorphosed or aqueously altered (they are assigned a number between 1 and 7). The largest part of Chondrites texture (60-80%) is made by *chondrules* that are made of small, round particles prominent among the components present in a metal matrix. Chondrules formed as molten or partially molten droplets in space before being accreted to their parent asteroids. The chondrules in a Chondrite that have not been altered are assigned with a '3'. Larger numbers indicate an increase in thermal metamorphosis up to a maximum of 7, where the chondrules have been destroyed. Numbers lower than 3 are given to Chondrites whose chondrules have been changed by the presence of water, down to 1, where the chondrules have been obliterated by this alteration. Chondrules can range in diameter from just a few micrometers to over 1 cm. Most chondrules are composed primarily of the silicate minerals *olivine* [(Mg,Fe)₂SiO₄] and *pyroxene* [XY(Si, Al)₂O₆], where X represents Ca, Na, Fe, Mg and Y represents Cr, Al, Mg, Co, Mn, Sc, Ti, V, Fe.

The chemical components of Chondrites formed during the birth of solar system and their abundance of nonvolatile elements are close to those of the solar nebula. These elements originated in dying stars and/or in stars collisions where later dispersed into the interstellar medium and where incorporated in the cloud of dust and gas from which the Solar System and hence our Earth was formed. Thus chondrites represent one of the oldest solid materials within the Solar System and are believed to be the building blocks of the planetary system.

Achondrites

Achondrites are stony meteorites that doesn't contain chondrules. They have been differentiated and reprocessed due to melting of the parent body.

Carbonaceous Chondrites

Carbonaceous Chondrites contain a high proportion of carbon (up to 3%), which is in the form of graphite, carbonates and organic compounds, including amino acids. One important sub-group is represented by the C1 type. This group has chemical compositions that is closest to that measured in the solar photosphere (aside from gaseous elements and other exceptions, such as Lithium). In this sense, they are chemically the most primitive known meteorites. C1 chondrites typically contain a high proportion of water (up to 22%). They have a composition of hydrous phyllosilicates, magnetite, and olivine crystals occurring in a black matrix, and a possible lack of chondrules.

Iron meteorites

Iron meteorites have an elemental composition consisting largely of nickel-iron alloys. These meteorites are thought to be fragment of the core of larger ancient asteroids that have shattered by impacts. A typical iron meteorite contains 80-90% Fe, 5-10% Ni, some per cent of Si and Mg, a little amount of Co, P, S and trace amount of over 20 other elements. The few percent of iron meteorites that contain silicate inclusions provide evidence for impacts between molten or partially molten planetesimal. The major source of melting was the content of short-lived nuclides (such as ²⁶Al and ⁶⁰Fe) producing high temperatures, in the early story of solar system. The iron contained in the early asteroids migrated because its high density, towards the core

of them. Iron meteorites are classified in several sub categories according to the amount of nickel and trace amounts of elements such as Ga, Ir, Ge corresponding to different parent asteroids

Pallasites

Pallasites are described by a certain structural class of stony-iron meteorites that contains abundant silicate inclusions in a nickel-iron matrix where usually the silicates are large olivine crystals. Sometimes they are used in jewelry because of its gem quality. One prevailing theory suggests that Pallasites originate from the remnants of large planetary bodies or asteroids. These bodies experienced a process called planetary differentiation, where intense heat and pressure caused heavy metallic elements like iron and nickel to sink toward the center, forming a dense metal core. Simultaneously, lighter silicate minerals, including crystallized olivine, remained in the outer layers. Pallasites may have formed at the interface between these layers.

Mesosiderites

Mesosiderites are composed of approximately equal parts of metallic nickel-iron and silicate.

They are composed by broken centimeter-sized fragments of minerals cemented together. These fragments contain a mix of solidified silicate and metal clasts.

Martian meteorites [4]

A Martian meteorite is a rock that formed on Mars, was ejected from the planet by an impact event, and traversed interplanetary space before landing on Earth as a meteorite. As of September 2020, less than half a percent of the 72,000 meteorites have been classified as Martian meteorites. The Martian meteorites are divided into three rare groups of achondritic (stony) meteorites: *shergottites nakhlites*, *chassignites*, and ones otherwise. In particular the shergottites are igneous rocks rich in magnesium and iron. The shergottites appear to have crystallized as recently as 180 million years ago, which is a surprisingly young age considering how ancient the majority of the surface of Mars appears to be.

3. Brief reminder on hand-held XRF spectrophotometry [5]

The XRF spectrophotometry (or x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy) is a non-destructive analysis technique that allows to know, in real time, the composition of a sample through the emission of x ray fluorescence radiation. The availability, now for over thirtyfive years, of portable versions equipped with software capable of data processing and showing the analysis on the instrument display or by downloading them to an associated PC, allows a wide range of applications.[6] The Fluorescence is the property of some substances to re-emit (in most cases with longer wavelength and therefore less energy) the electromagnetic radiation received. In particular this is the case when the incident radiation and the reissued radiation belong to the x-ray spectrum. The basic mechanism is as follows: when the incident beam is characterized by appropriate energy and intensity, it is possible to create, for photoelectric effect, a vacancy in an inner shell of the atom of a given element. The system thus goes in an imbalanced condition, which can be re-established when another electron with less energy replaces the vacancy, freeing up a photon that therefore has an energy equal to the difference between the electron energies in the two initial and final positions. The x-fluorescence radiation emitted by a chemical element has a characteristic spectrum which depend on their energy. The x-ray fluorescence energies are tabulated for all elements which make them in principle recognizable and distinguishable from any other element. The X-ray energies generally used (dozens of keV) involve almost exclusively the electrons of the inner K, L, M shells, so the chemical bonds are not altered. The XRF spectrophotometry is therefore a non-destructive analysis widely used in many fields such as metal recognition, metallurgy, catalysis, semiconductor production, plastics analysis, precious metals analysis, biology, geology, archaeology, painting, food technologies and others.

It must be remembered that the examination of the characteristic x ray fluorescence emitted by atoms identifies with great confidence the individual chemical elements but not the compositions, if they are in the form of compounds. There are essentially two limitations to the XRF technique: (a) due to their low fluorescence energy, it is difficult to detect elements with energies below about 2 Kev (e.g., oxygen,) and of

course elements whose fluorescence energy is above the energy of photons of primary x radiation; (b) the x-rays penetration increases with their primary energy and decreases with the density of the sample material in a range from a few microns to a few hundred microns. This translates into practice in the fact that XRF technology is only applicable for analyzing thin surface layers of the sample.

A modern XRF equipment consists of the following main components: a miniaturized x-ray generator tube, a solid-state detection system of fluorescence radiation (generally silicon-lithium), an electronic system that transforms analog signals into digital and sorts them according to their energy through a multichannel analyzer. The signals are sent to a computer for processing the data in form of an x-ray fluorescence spectrum which, by showing the number of counts as a function of energy, makes it possible to recognize rather easily the peaks characteristic of each element. In modern portable systems this recognition is done directly by the computer built into the instrument itself. The data are shown on the display of the instrument, in form of spectra or directly in terms of the percentage of concentration of the individual element, with a confidence coefficient of more than 95%. The instrument can be equipped with different measuring modes, according to the type of samples to be analyzed: 'Soil', 'Mining' and 'General Metals'. A library of hundreds of metal alloys is also downloaded into the instrument's computer. This allows to immediately recognize a particular alloy when the percent of the elements present in the sample matches the composition of such an alloy.

3.1 XRF equipment used for testing and testing procedure

The instrument used in this study was the NITON XL3t GOLDD+XRF spectrometer manufactured by the leading USA company *Thermo Fisher Analytics*.² The abovementioned XRF model is the most advanced version of the series, capable of detecting light elements such as Silicon, Magnesium, Aluminum (very important in analysis of meteorite composition) and precious metals.

Figure 1– (a) Portable XRF equipment block scheme and (b) actual picture of the instrument

For stony and stony-iron and even iron meteorites the 'mining' mode appeared the more suitable for the sample types studied, because the instrument takes into account the total percent of elements (mainly oxygen) that are not directly recognized, referred as 'balance'. Instead, with 'general metal' setting, the analyzer would assume that only metals are in the sample thus resulting in misleading compositions. A single analysis procedure allows the simultaneous detection of over eighty elements. The analysis duration for each sample can vary from 60 to 120 seconds. Longer is the time better is the accuracy, but above a certain limit there is no further gain but only X-ray anode consumption. Limit of detection (LOD) for each analyte is two times the standard deviation of the concentration measured in samples.

² Represented in Italy by *Sirio Analytics Srl* of Lodi (Milan)

In this study it was adopted, for each sample, a measurement duration of 120 seconds. The values reported are the average of four measurements taken in different points of the sample, except for the Martian meteorite, too small. The collimator (beam size) was the standard 8 mm.

4. Results and comparison with literature data

Table I reports the type, the characteristics and the summarized classification of the samples analyzed. Tables II shows the Solar photosphere abundances of elements, literature data on a C1 type Chondrite and the results of the XRF analysis in comparison with literature for data for H type, Rumuruti and carbonaceous Chondrites. The carbonaceous Chondrite NWA 16685 CK6 analyzed, very rare, was found in 2022 in the Sahara desert: probably this is the first time that its composition is reported. Table III reports the results of the XRF analysis of Pallasite Sericho, analysis of metallic and Martian meteorites in comparison with the literature data. Probably, due to quite recent discovery of the Sericho Pallasite in Kenia (2017) the author did not find literature reference of composition for this sample.

The data of columns two and three of table II, the elemental composition of the solar system, are taken from a recent paper of K. Lodders [7], one of the world's leading experts. In the original paper the values are given as atom abundances: they have been recalculated in terms of mass per cent.

As it is well known from the basic literature of comparison of on solar composition with that of meteorites [8] the last are depleted in noble gases and H, He C, N, O. In particular the ratio Sun/Meteorite is 2.06 for oxygen, 38.4 for nitrogen, 9.46 for carbon. In addition, elements such as Li, Be, B, F, Na are too light for being detected by the XRF technique. However, these elements in meteorites account in total for less than 0.5%, thus in first approximation can be ignored. When set on the 'mining' mode the XRF instrument recognizes the presence in the sample of the fraction of elements too light for being distinguished, but their total is reported in per cent as 'balance'. In addition, for a correct comparison between the abundance of the elements in solar photosphere and in meteorites (in particular the C1 type), the data of column two have been 'normalized' for elements absent or depleted in meteorites using the abovementioned sun/meteorite ratios and including the Na (that accounts for less than 1%) and reported in column three.

All materials from the solar system so far studied show various degrees of depletion for elements depending on condensation temperature. Thus, the different depletion amounts are characteristic for each meteorite class. The least depleted type of chondrite is the rare C1 (or Ivuna-type) carbonaceous Chondrites. It is thought they have not been heated above 50 °C, indicating that they condensed in the cooler outer portion of the solar nebula to which they are similar in composition (aside from gaseous elements, and elements such as lithium). In addition, the radiometric dating shows that the age of C1 type Chondrites matches that of formation of solar system. For this reason, they are commonly used as a reference to which other meteorites are compared. Together with CI type Chondrites, the least differentiated materials are the other carbonaceous Chondrites, Enstatite and ordinary Chondrites. Their relative abundances of refractory elements are similar to the solar abundances for elements. This is confirmed by the results shown in table II where only the carbonaceous Chondrite of C1 type provides the best match with solar abundances [7]. Unfortunately, the author was not able to procure a C1 type Chondrite for XRF analysis to compare with K. Lodder findings.

In the tables II and III the fractions of 'balance' are reported in the bottom. In order to better compare the most relevant literature references with the results of this paper the data in such references of elements that differ by more than 20% with this work are marked in corsive. As it can be seen for H Chondrites the major discrepancies are with Lodder, although the values for Fe, Mg, and Si are consistent among them. The analysis on the NW869 chondrite have been conducted for both the bulk and the crust of the sample, showing some depletion in Ca, Mg, and S, possibly due to atmospheric ablation during falling on the Earth, but also some enrichment in Ni and K perhaps due to high temperature promoted interdiffusion or contamination by terrestrial soil. For CK Chondrite the major discrepancies are again with Lodder (except for Fe and Si). For the Rumuruti Chondrite the consistency with other authors holds for Fe, Si, Ca, Cr, Ti, Zn. An important large discrepancy is that for Sulfur.

For the Sericho Pallasite there is not reference. For the metallic meteorite there is little significance to make a direct comparison aside the confirmation of 83-93% Fe and 5-7% Ni.

Finally, the Martian shergottite, confirms although with concentration differences of about 30%, the findings of Shirai et al. [13] and in particular, besides Fe, Si, Mg the rich presence of Al and Ca.

Table I. – Type, characteristics, summarized classifications and pictures of the samples analyzed

Name /classification	Chondrite NWA 869	Rumuruti Chondrite Grizim 001	Carbonaceous chondrite NWA 15685	Carbonaceous chondrite NWA 14110	Pallasite Sericho	Metallic meteorite	Martian Meteorite NWA 7397
Location /year	Sahara desert 2000	Algeria 2021	Sahara 2022	Algeria 2021	Kenya 2016	Campo del Cielo-Argentina 1576	Marocco/2012
Type	L-3-6	R3	CK6	CO3	-	-	Shergottite
Weight (g)	21.5	16.8	11	4.56	19.35	36.67	0.61
Volume (cm ³)	7.2	5.65	1.77	~1.1	6	4.6	~0.24
Density (g/cm ³)	2.99	2.97	6.21	4.15	3.22	7.97	~2.5
Summary of classification of The Meteoritical Society. [1]	Fusion crust polished and ablated by wind erosion (terrestrial age 4.4 ± 0.7 ka. Chondritic breccia consisting of about 75% volume L-chondrite clasts. Olivine [(Mg, Fe)2SiO4] and low-Ca pyroxene [XY(Si,Al)O6] in lithic clasts.	Apparently, this very rare type of chondrites come from an asteroid's regolite. The brecciated chondrite texture is composed of 45% volume chondrules with an average diameter of 0.47 mm. Additional mineral are chromite and phosphates. Fe/Mn olivine=64, Fe/Mn matrix = 87.7 NiO=0.1%. Low Ca pyroxene.	Recrystallized chondritic with large dispersed chondrules with average diameter of about 0.45 mm in a recrystallized matrix composed of olivine (Fe/Mn=103) of high Ca pyroxene, and Cr-plagioclase and Cr-bearing magnetite.	Chondritic texture composed by abundant FeO-rich olivine chondrules of average diameter of 0.2 mm. Additional hercynitic spinels, chromite, FeNi metal, troilite and apatite. Low Ca pyroxene	Olivine grain 0.5-1cm across 70% volume. Kamacite (Fe-Ni alloy with Ni less than 7%) around olivine with plessite pockets. Rare metals region show typical Widmanstätten pattern. FeO/MnO=57, C ₂ O ₃ =0.03, P=0.06	This type of meteorites were classified as iron meteorite octahedrite with silicate inclusions.	Large oikocrystals (magmatic rock with crystals of low Ca pyroxene enclosing crystals of olivine and Cr rich chromite. Olivine contains sparse melt inclusions of K-Na-Si- rich glass surrounded by post-shock microfractures. Olivine:FeO/MnO=47.54

Table II. - Solar photosphere abundances of elements, C1 literature data and results of the XRF analysis and comparison with literature for H type, Rumuruti and carbonaceous chondrites. The data are in per cent of mass.

Element	Solar photosphere spectroscopy composition Lodder [7]	Normalized solar photosphere composition	Cl Chond.			H Chondrites				Romuruti Chondrites					Carbonaceous chondrites CK		Carbonaceous Chondrite CO	
			Lodder [7]	This paper (NW 869)	XRF Metzler et al. (NWA 869) [9] *	Lodder [7] (L type)	This paper	Schulze et al. [10]	Isa [11]	XRF Palme et al. [11]	XRF/IN AA Dar Al Gani [11]	This paper (CK6)	Lodder [7] (CK)	This paper (CO3)	Lodder [7] (CO)			
Al	0.0053	0.82	Bulk 2.39	3.82	1.09	1.17	1.99	1.11	1.05	1.07	4.00	1.53	1.95	1.4				
Ca	0.006	0.93	1.66	1.28	1.44	1.3	1.32	1.3	1.23	1.25	2.18	1.63	1.35	1.57				
Cl	0.00005	0.0078	0.071	0.185		0.001	0.094				0.077	0.023	0.057	0.029				
Cr	0.00159	0.247	0.366	0.354	0.42	0.366	0.398	0.38	0.358	0.348	0.281	0.362	0.384	0.355				
Co	0.00037	0.058	0.09	0		0.06	0.041	0.068	0.071	0.0267	0.083	0.062	0.062	0.068				
Cu	0.00007	0.011	0.005	0		0.001	0.012				0.007	0.01	0.012	0.0134				
Fe	0.1242	19.32	18.06	18.68	22.1	21.85	26.87	24.5	24.4	24.3	22.14	23.5	26.36	24.8				
Mg	0.0648	10.07	10.68	8.72	9.57	14.86	7.45	13.16	13.78	12.49	6.17	14.6	10.06	14.5				
Mn	0.0013	0.2	0.326	0.336	0.263	0.258	0.244	0.23	0.226	0.208	0.175	0.144	0.166	0.164				
Ni	0.0068	1.06	0.281	0.438	1.37	1.27	0.474	1.56	1.44	0.287	0.416	1.32	1.03	1.41				
P	0.00058	0.09	0.131	0.087	0.098	0.1	0.078		0.126	0.132	0.095	0.11	0.076	0.115				
S	0.0332	5.18	2.07	0.901		2.2	0.436	4.14			0.117	1.6	0.906	2.18				
Si	0.0668	10.39	18.89	18.2	20.79	18.46	14.02		16.69	16.92	15.96	15.8	13.96	15.8				
K	0.00031	0.048	0.334	0.498		0.088	0.342	0.069	0.0735	0.075	0.371	0.035	0.255	0.036				
Ti	0.0003	0.047	0.078	0.099	0.072	0.069	0.057		0.057	0.058	0.105	0.077	0.076	0.075				
V	0.00003	0.0047	0.023	0.028	0.0084	0.0075	0.034	0.007		0.0067	0.03	0.009	0.003	0.009				
Zn	0.00018	0.028	0.007	0.007	0.0055	0.0054	0.014	0.0165	0.015	0.016	0.01	0.009	0.008	0.01				
H	73.46					0.126						0.48		0.1				
He	24.68																	
Ar	0.0084																	
Ne	0.42																	
C	0.26	0.04										0.1		0.49				
O	0.616	42.63										38.26		36.42				
N	0.073	0.028										0.006		0.037				
Na	0.0027	0.39				0.69	0.69	0.69	0.63	0.54		0.32		0.405				
Balance	0.331		44.54	46.32	38.47	37.92	46.07	44.12			47.03	39.2		37.47				

TABLE III- Results of the XRF analysis and comparison with literature for data for Pallasite Sericho, Metallic and Martian meteorites. The data are in per cent of mass.

Element	Pallasite Sericho			Metallic			Martian Shergottite	
	Average of 4 different points	Olivine proximity	Fe-Ni matrix proximity	This paper	Gemelli et al. [12] XRF	From the official classification	This paper	Yamato Y980459 [13] *
Al	0.576	0.446	0.601	1.64	-		3.72	2.74
As	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.012	-		0	
Ba	-	0.008	0.008	0.013	-		0	
Ag	0.01	0.007	0	0.026	-		0	
Ca	0.046	0.1	0	0.096	-		3.17	4.88
Cl	0.146	0.074	0.086	0.092	-		0.017	
Cr	0.031	0.046	0.043	0.023	0.097		0.341	0.47
Co	0.09	0.09	0.094	0.426	0.32	0.43	0	
Cu	0.004	0	0.008	0.008	-		0	
Fe	23.96	17.41	26.65	83.67	92.7	92.6	17.84	13.45
Mg	5.54	5.07	5.41	3.63	-		6.18	11.3
Mn	0.095	0.132	0.099	0	-		0.4	0.37
Ni	0.692	0.395	0.989	5.11	6.6	6.68	0.02	
Si	7.35	8.79	7.16	2.05	0		16.96	23.32
S	1.62	0.242	1.02	0.047	0.013		0.12	
P	0.042	0.037	0.067	0.391	0.012	0.25	0.235	
K	0.177	0.207	0.0224	0.379	0		0.297	
Ti	0	0.008	0.009	0	0		0.25	0.32
V	0.009	0.015	0.02	0.04	-		0.033	
Zn	0.003			0	-		0.032	
W				0.078	0.051			
Balance	59.6	66.9	57.48	2.4			50.19	

(*) In the original paper the data are reported in form of oxides. The value in the column have been recalculated in form of pure elements

The presence of the abovementioned discrepancies it is not so surprising. Even when comparing samples of meteorites with the same origin and classification one can expect that different fragments of the same bigger stone, while confirming the presence of the same major constituents, could have elemental composition variable to a certain extent. Even more, if the comparison is made between the same 'type' of meteorites but from different findings, as in the case of H, Rumuruti and carbonaceous Chondrites. Of course, one must also take into account that different analytical techniques, calibration tolerances of the same technique in different laboratories as well as instruments limitations can be sources of discrepancies of the final data.

References

- [1] <https://www.britannica.com/science/meteorite/Alteration-processes>
- [2] <https://meteoritical.org/>
- [3] Meteoritical Bulletin Database, Dec.2021
- [4] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Martian_meteorite
- [5] <https://www.nitonuk.co.uk/pdf/Niton%20XRF%20Guide.pdf>
- [6] L. Rosai, *Giornale di Fisica*, Vol.61, 15-32 (2020)
- [7] K. Lodders, *Space Science Reviews* 217,3, (2021)
- [8] H. Palme and A. Jones, volume 1, pp. 41–61, © 2003, Elsevier Lt -Solar System Abundances of the Elements
- [9] K. Metzger et al., *Meteoritic & planetary science* 46, N. 5, 662-680, (2011)
- [10] H. Schulze et al., *Meteoritics*, volume 29, 2, 275-286. March 1994
- [11] J. Isa et al., *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 124, 1 January 2014, 131-151
- [12] M. Gemelli et al., *Geostandards and Geoanalytical Research* · March 2014, 1-15
- [13] N. Shirai et al., *Antarctic Meteorite Research*, Vol. 17, p.55 (2004)